

Formulation and Evaluation of a Plant-Based Protein Bar Using Underutilized Ancient Grains Amaranth and Quinoa

¹P Sindhu Lahari and ²Anil Bukya

¹Department of Life Sciences and Nutrition, Capital Degree and PG College - Shapur Nagar, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

²School of Nutrition and Dietetics, Symbiosis Skills and Professional University, Pune, Maharashtra, India

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Corresponding Author: Anil Bukya

Abstract

The increasing consumer demand for health-focused, plant-based snack options has driven interest in the use of ancient grains in functional food products. The present study focuses on the formulation and comprehensive evaluation of a plant-based protein bar utilizing underutilized ancient grains, amaranth and quinoa, known for their superior nutritional profiles. Three variants of protein bars (T₁, T₂, and T₃) were developed by combining cooked amaranth, quinoa, oats, and flavored plant-based protein powders, along with natural binders and additives. The bars were analyzed for proximate composition, mineral and vitamin content, antioxidant activity, sensory attributes, and microbial safety. Results revealed a nutritionally balanced product with high protein content (19.2 g/100 g), significant dietary fiber (10 g/100 g), and essential micronutrients such as iron (4.8 mg/100 g) and calcium (80 mg/100 g). Sensory evaluation indicated good consumer acceptability across all samples, with the strawberry-flavored protein bar variant scoring highest in taste. Microbial analysis confirmed the product's safety and shelf stability over 30 days under ambient conditions. The findings validate the potential of integrating amaranth and quinoa in functional snack formulations, addressing the demand for clean-label, gluten-free, and nutrient-dense plant-based protein products. This study supports the development of sustainable, health-promoting snacks that align with contemporary dietary trends.

Keywords: Amaranth, quinoa, protein bar, ancient grains, functional foods, nutritional analysis, sensory evaluation

1. Introduction

In recent years, consumer interest in plant-based and Functional foods has risen significantly due to increasing awareness of the relationship between Diet and overall health. Functional foods are recognized not only for their basic nutritional benefits but also for their ability to promote health and reduce the risk of Chronic Diseases (Granato *et al.*, 2020) [7].

Ancient grains such as amaranth (*Amaranthus caudatus*) and Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*) are distinguished from modern cereals by their superior protein quality, rich dietary fiber content and abundance of essential Micronutrients including Iron, Calcium and Magnesium (Bouis & Saltzman, 2017) [2]. Unlike many conventional grains, both Amaranth and Quinoa contain all nine essential amino acids, making them complete protein sources suitable for vegetarian and vegan diets (Vega-Galvez *et al.*, 2010) [18]. Furthermore, their gluten-free nature makes them ideal for individuals with celiac disease or gluten intolerance, addressing a growing dietary concern among consumers

(Sharma & Singh, 2018) [15].

The integration of ancient grains into modern snack formulations-such as energy bars-provides an effective delivery system for these nutritional benefits while aligning with consumer preferences for convenience and clean-label products. Protein bars are particularly popular among athletes, fitness enthusiasts and health-conscious individuals due to their portability and targeted macronutrient composition (Samuel & Peerkhan, 2020) [12]. Despite their commercial success, many available products rely heavily on synthetic additives or animal-based proteins, creating demand for cleaner, plant-based alternatives with comparable or improved nutritional profiles.

From a sustainability perspective, amaranth and quinoa offer significant advantages. These crops are well-adapted to harsh climates and require fewer inputs compared to many modern cereals, making them suitable for sustainable agricultural systems (FAO, 2013) [4]. Their revival also contributes to agrobiodiversity and the preservation of traditional agricultural knowledge.

While previous studies have explored protein enrichment and antioxidant properties in grain-based snack bars (Gonçalves & Silva, 2021; Semwal *et al.*, 2018) [6, 13, 14], limited research exists on the synergistic nutritional and sensory potential of combining amaranth and quinoa in a single functional product. Moreover, the food industry continues to seek formulations that strike an optimal balance between taste, texture, and nutritional value to ensure consumer acceptability and long-term market success. This study aims to formulate and evaluate a high-protein, gluten-free energy bar using amaranth and quinoa, with a focus on nutritional composition, sensory attributes, and microbial safety for functional food applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Ingredient Procurement

The core ingredients for the formulation were sourced from local organic-certified suppliers in Hyderabad, India. Ancient grains-amaranth and quinoa were obtained in whole seed form, while rolled oats, plant-based protein powder, nut butter, natural sweeteners (honey), chopped nuts, dried fruits and dark chocolate chips were acquired from recognized health food distributors. All ingredients were stored in airtight containers under controlled temperature and humidity until use, in compliance with standard food safety protocols (FAO/WHO, 2009) [9].

2.2 Product Preparation for Protein Bar

2.2.1 Pre-treatment of Grains

Amaranth and quinoa were rinsed thoroughly and boiled in a 1:2 grain-to-water ratio for 10 minutes to reduce antinutritional factors such as saponins and phytic acid and to enhance digestibility (Ruales & Nair, 1993) [11]. The cooked grains were drained, cooled and partially dried to remove surface moisture.

2.2.2 Formulation and Mixing

A base formulation was developed with a 60:40 amaranth-to-quinoa ratio, combined with oats and protein powder. Wet ingredients (honey and nut butter) were gently heated to reduce viscosity, then incorporated into the dry mixture. Chopped nuts, dried fruits, and dark chocolate chips were folded in for taste and texture enhancement. The mixture was stirred until a cohesive, sticky consistency was achieved.

2.2.3 Formulation of T₁, T₂ and T₃ Protein Bar

Table 1 outlines the standardized formulation used for the development of three treatment variants (T₁, T₂ and T₃) of the ancient grain protein bar. All three samples incorporated identical base ingredients, including cooked amaranth (100 g), cooked quinoa (150 g), rolled oats (250 g), nut butter (200 g), honey or agave syrup (100 g), chopped nuts/seeds (30 g), dried fruits (30 g) and dark chocolate chips (40 g), ensuring consistency in macronutrient contributions and textural properties across samples. The primary variation among the formulations was the type of protein powder used-T₁ and T₃ included strawberry-flavored plant protein, while T₂ incorporated caffe latte-flavored protein powder. This flavor-based differentiation aimed to assess potential sensory variation due to protein flavoring, while maintaining a consistent nutritional baseline. The uniform

inclusion of nutrient-dense ingredients such as oats, seeds and ancient grains provided a rich matrix of complex carbohydrates, essential amino acids, dietary fiber and natural sweeteners, contributing to the functional and palatable nature of the final product.

2.3 Procedure Flowchart for preparation of Protein Bar

Fig 1: Flowchart of Protein Bar

Table 1: Composition of T₁, T₂ and T₃ Protein Bar

Ingredients	T ₁ Sample	T ₂ Sample	T ₃ Sample
Amaranth (Cooked)	100 g	100 g	100 g
Quinoa (Cooked)	150 g	150 g	150 g
Oats	250 g	250 g	250 g
Protein powder	100 g (Strawberry)	100 g (Caffe Latte)	100 g (Strawberry)
Nut butter	200 g	200 g	200 g
Honey or agave	100 g	100 g	100 g
Chopped nuts/seeds	30 g	30 g	30 g
Dried fruits	30 g	30 g	30 g
Choco chips	40 g	40 g	40 g

2.4 Sensory Evaluation

A sensory panel consisting of 20 semi-trained judges was formed at a Hyderabad-based academic food lab. Evaluations were performed under standardized conditions using a 7-point hedonic scale (1 = dislike very much, 7 = like very much) to assess: Each sample (T₁, T₂, T₃) was coded and presented in random order. Results were statistically analyzed using one-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$).

2.5 Proximate Composition

The formulated bars were analyzed for moisture, ash, protein, fat, fiber and carbohydrate content using *AOAC Official Methods* (AOAC, 2019) [1]: Moisture by Oven drying at 105 °C (AOAC 925.10); Ash: Muffle furnace at 550 °C (AOAC 923.03); Protein by Kjeldahl method (AOAC 992.23) with a nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor of 6.25; Fat by Soxhlet extraction using petroleum ether (AOAC 996.06); Fiber by Acid-alkali digestion method (AOAC 985.29); Carbohydrates by Calculated by difference

2.6 Mineral Analysis and Vitamin Analysis

Levels of iron, calcium, and sodium were measured using atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS) in accordance with AOAC 984.27. Vitamins were AOAC protocols:

Vitamin A (retinol): AOAC 992.04; Vitamin E (tocopherol): AOAC 992.03; Vitamin C (ascorbic acid): AOAC 984.26

2.7 Microbial Analysis and Shelf-Life Study

Microbial load was evaluated immediately post-production and over storage (0, 15, and 30 days) at ambient conditions. The following microbial tests were performed: Total Aerobic Plate Count: AOAC 999.12; Yeast and Mold Count: AOAC 997.02; Enterobacteriaceae and *Staphylococcus aureus*: AOAC 991.14. All microbiological assays ensured the product met food safety standards as defined by the Codex Alimentarius (FAO/WHO, 2009) [9]. Product shelf life was considered acceptable based on microbial limits and sensory quality retention over 30 days.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Sensory Evaluation

The sensory evaluation of the three protein bar formulations (T₁, T₂, T₃) was conducted using a 7-point hedonic scale, where 1 indicated “dislike extremely” and 7 indicated “like extremely.” The results, summarized in Table 2, show that all samples received favorable scores across evaluated attributes-color, taste, smell and texture-suggesting good overall acceptability. T₃, formulated with strawberry-flavored protein, achieved the highest mean score for taste (6.40 ± 0.50), indicating it was the most preferred in terms of flavor. T₁ also performed well in color (6.40 ± 0.60) and smell (6.40 ± 0.60), while T₂, which incorporated coffee latte-flavored protein, showed slightly lower scores for color (6.10 ± 0.45) and smell (6.20 ± 0.41), though still within an acceptable range. Texture scores were consistent across samples, with T₁ and T₂ both receiving 6.20 and T₃ slightly lower at 6.05 ± 0.39. These variations suggest that while flavoring of protein powder can influence sensory perception, particularly in taste and aroma, the base formulation offers a robust textural foundation. The positive reception aligns with findings from previous studies indicating that incorporation of ancient grains and natural binders can enhance palatability in functional snack bars (Sharma & Singh, 2018; Gonçalves & Silva, 2021) [15, 6]. Overall, the sensory data support the feasibility of using amaranth and quinoa in consumer-acceptable, protein-rich snack products.

Table 2: Sensory parameters of Ancient Grain Protein Bar Tested sample (T₁, T₂, T₃)

Attribute	T ₁ (Mean ± SD)	T ₂ (Mean ± SD)	T ₃ (Mean ± SD)
Color	6.40 ± 0.60	6.10 ± 0.45	6.35 ± 0.49
Taste	6.05 ± 0.51	6.20 ± 0.41	6.40 ± 0.50
Smell	6.40 ± 0.60	6.20 ± 0.41	6.25 ± 0.55
Texture	6.20 ± 0.70	6.20 ± 0.52	6.05 ± 0.39

3.2 Proximate Composition

The proximate analysis of the formulated ancient grain protein bar reveals a well-balanced nutritional profile suitable for health-conscious consumers, athletes and individuals seeking plant-based dietary options. As shown in Table 3, the energy content was measured at 390.1 kcal per 100 g, which aligns with typical values for functional snack bars and provides adequate caloric density for an energy-boosting product. The protein content was notably high at 19.2 g/100 g, confirming the product's suitability as

a protein-enriched snack. This value reflects the synergistic combination of high-protein ingredients such as quinoa, amaranth, and plant-based protein powder. The carbohydrate level was 43 g/100 g, serving as a key energy source, while the total fat content was moderate at 15.7 g/100 g, primarily contributed by nut butter and seeds. Importantly, the dietary fiber content was 10 g/100 g, exceeding many conventional snack bars, thereby offering benefits for digestive health and satiety. The moisture content of 16% falls within acceptable limits for semi-moist snack bars and suggests good potential for moderate shelf-life stability. These findings are consistent with prior studies on ancient grain-based bars, where high protein and fiber levels were associated with improved nutritional value and consumer appeal (Semwal *et al.*, 2018; Gonçalves & Silva, 2021) [13, 14, 6]. Overall, the nutritional composition supports the product's classification as a functional food with significant health-promoting potential.

3.3 Vitamin and Mineral Profile

The vitamin and mineral analysis of the formulated ancient grain protein bar underscores its potential as a functional snack with added micronutrient value. As detailed in Table 3, the bar contained vitamin A at 0.03 mg/100 g, vitamin E at 3.76 mg/100 g, and vitamin C at 2 mg/100 g. Although vitamin A content was modest, the presence of vitamin E, a potent lipid-soluble antioxidant, contributes significantly to oxidative stability and may support immune and skin health. The presence of vitamin C, a water-soluble antioxidant, adds further nutritional advantage, aiding in collagen synthesis and enhancing non-heme iron absorption from plant sources (Gul *et al.*, 2021) [8]. Mineral analysis (Table 3) revealed that the product was a good source of iron (4.8 mg/100 g) and calcium (80 mg/100 g), addressing common deficiencies prevalent in vegetarian and vegan populations (Sharma & Singh, 2018) [15]. The iron content, in particular, is notable given the plant-based formulation, supported by ingredients like quinoa, amaranth and nuts, all naturally rich in non-heme iron. Additionally, the sodium level of 180 mg/100 g was within moderate limits, contributing to flavor without exceeding dietary sodium recommendations. These results align with previous studies emphasizing the mineral density of ancient grains and their suitability in developing nutrient-dense functional foods (Gonçalves & Silva, 2021; Srinivasan & Rani, 2014) [6, 16]. Overall, the micronutrient composition supports the formulation's role in promoting health and preventing micronutrient deficiencies.

Table 3: Vitamin Analysis of the formulated Ancient Grain Protein Bar

Test parameter	Unit	Results	Test method
Vitamin A	mg/100gm	0.03	AOAC 992.04
Vitamin E	mg/100gm	3.76	AOAC 992.03
Vitamin C	mg/100gm	2	AOAC 984.26
Iron	mg/100gm	4.8	AOAC 984.27
Calcium	mg/100gm	80	AOAC 984.27
Sodium	mg/100gm	180	AOAC 923.03

3.4 Microbial Safety Analysis

The microbial assessment of the formulated ancient grain protein bar demonstrated excellent microbiological quality

and safety suitable for human consumption. As shown in Table 4, the aerobic plate count and yeast & mold counts were both below 10 CFU/g, well within the acceptable limits of 1×10 CFU/g prescribed by AOAC standards (AOAC, 2016). The absence of Enterobacteriaceae and *Staphylococcus aureus* in 25 g samples further confirms the product's hygienic processing conditions and its safety profile. These results suggest effective control of microbial contamination during production, packaging and storage, thereby extending the product's shelf life and reducing the risk of foodborne illness. Comparable microbial safety levels have been reported in similar cereal-based protein bars, emphasizing the importance of stringent quality control measures in ready-to-eat functional foods (Gupta *et al.*, 2019; Kumar & Sharma, 2020) [9, 10]. Overall, the microbial analysis validates the ancient grain protein bar as a microbiologically safe and shelf-stable product.

Table 4: Microbial Activity of the formulated Ancient Grain Protein Bar

Test Parameter	Unit	Result	Limits	Method
Aerobic plate count	CFU/g	<10	1×10	AOAC 999.12
Yeast & molds	CFU/g	<10	1×10	AOAC 997.02
Enterobacteriaceae	CFU/g	Absent	Absent/25g	AOAC 991.14
<i>S. aureus</i>	CFU/25g	Absent	Absent/25g	AOAC 991.14

4. Conclusion

The formulated ancient grain protein bar demonstrated excellent sensory acceptance, balanced nutritional composition and strong microbiological safety, validating its potential as a functional snack. The integration of amaranth, quinoa, and oats, complemented by natural protein powders and sweeteners, resulted in a product with significant protein content, dietary fiber, essential vitamins, and minerals. The microbial quality ensured its shelf stability and safety for consumption. This study highlights the feasibility of utilizing underexploited ancient grains in convenient, nutrient-dense products that align with modern dietary trends and consumer preferences. Future research may focus on extended shelf-life studies and *in vivo* health impact assessments to further substantiate its benefits.

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